

TEACHERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS ONLINE TEACHING AND LEARNING DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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ABSTRACT

The emergency COVID 19 Lockdown was a preventive measure that disrupted the lives of students, parents and teachers. To cope up with this crisis, the education sector started conducting online classes. The present study aims at the attitude of teachers of West Bengal towards online teaching and learning during the period of COVID 19 pandemic along with their gender and location. The findings of the study concluded that there is no significant difference in attitude towards online teaching and learning in terms of Gender. The research findings also revealed that locality has significant effect on teachers' attitude towards online teaching and learning.

Keywords: Attitude, Online Learning, COVID 19, Pandemic, Gender

INTRODUCTION

The COVID 19 Pandemic has created a global awareness that the current way of life does not work. There is a need for revolutionary change in many areas and it has become clear, one of them is the education sector. In West Bengal, Indian educational institutions/ universities were closed from mid March 2020 due to the rapid spread of COVID 19. The corona virus affected our normal life in every possible way. An unapproachable global lockdown has not only made our lives miserable, but forced us to live indoors. Government of India announced that we have to adapt to this environment by maintaining social distance among themselves (MoHA, 2020). The lockdown affects almost all sectors which have a major impact on the economy of most countries (Stefana et al., 2020).

Some sectors have reopened after the lockdown period of 50-70 days (Naik, et al., 2021). However, educational institutions had to remain closed for more than one year and a half as social distancing was difficult to maintain in place. This significantly disrupted teaching and learning of students in schools, colleges and universities. It was expected that the lockdown would affect the learning process to a great extent (Singh, 2021). Lockdown has forced all schools, colleges and universities to cancel their regular classes, semester exams etc. and switch to online mode. Initially, the teachers and students were quite confused and did not understand how to deal with this sudden crisis epidemic situation which stopped the educational activities (Singh, 2021). But it doesn't actually happen. After sometime, they realized that the lockdown due to COVID 19 has credited many changes and opportunities to strengthen their knowledge and infrastructure and switch to fully online mode for their regular classes and exams.

All credit goes to technologically advanced tools or applications in education. Teachers have created what's app group to share/send content to students and solve problems faced by students. Several applications like what's app, YouTube, Zoom, Google meet class, etc. have been used to teach students at home (Singh, 2021). Teachers from home prepare their lessons and share them using technologically advanced applications such as what's app and YouTube etc (Singh, 2021). Online classes can have many benefits for both faculty and students. For teachers, online classes allow new methods of teaching with access to advanced tools and technology involved and can reach many students (Appana, 2020). Contrary, student can gain knowledge of using various online tools and methods, pay close attention to recorded / live conversations of world class professionals, listen and watch classes multiple times, and work at their own pace (Arkorful & Abaidoo, 2015).

Online class can have many disadvantages for both faculty and students. Inability to connect with students' face to face and facilitate free conversation, discussion and mentoring lack of online teaching and learning experience consuming more time and practical, technical difficulties with high speed internet access from all locations and getting used to and valuing online teaching and learning are identified as key limitations (Arasaratnam-Smith & Northcote, 2017; Claywell et al., 2016; Sun & Chen, 2016).

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to UNESCO-IESALC (2020) there is a huge potential to equip technology in order to participate in quality education opportunities, access advanced information and knowledge, and enable them to participate in society. In Schools and colleges classrooms, effective integration of information and communication technology can be educated and empower students. Therefore, to ensure the quality of teachers and the quality of education, teachers have the ability to integrate ICT in their professional practice. Teacher who has acquired ICT in their professional teaching practice will be able to guide students to provide quality education and to develop ICT skills (Hermanto, 2020).

Almahasees, Mohsen & Amin (2021) in Jordon conducted a study to identify both the faculty and students of online learning. The study revealed that that both the faculty and the students agreed that online learning was effective during the epidemic. At the same time, it is less effective than face to-face learning. They also indicate that there are challenges of online learning, especially for deaf and hearing problems, lack of interaction and motivation, technical and internet issues, data privacy, and security. They have accepted the many advantages of online learning, such as self-learning, low cost, convenience and flexibility, face to face learning. Although this online learning is a temporary option in the COVID 19 pandemic situation. This study further recommended that Blended learning would provide a complete learning environment.

Covid 19 pandemic, forced teachers to change online teaching from face to face in the instant period. School to University level teachers applied online guidelines using a variety of online platform to prepare or personally to continue online instruction by their institutions. More than half of the respondents' teachers did not face the problem during the implementation of online learning and in most cases, it was satisfied. It is in line with the fact that most teachers

are ready to implement online teaching-learning in addition to conventional mode after Covid 19 pandemic end (Hermanto, 2020).

Srivastava & Srivastava (2022) in Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh conducted a study aimed to understand the perception of online teaching in rural and urban areas schools' teachers. The study indicated that both urban and rural area teachers do not believe that online classes will replace traditional classroom teaching. Teachers are also facing challenges in the lack of proper training, especially among the teachers or rural areas.

Today we are in the era of e-learning or online teaching and learning and it is very important to make students and teachers aware of the importance and usefulness of online teaching and learning or e-learning. Therefore, the present study will help to know how teachers react and think about online teaching and learning and what is their attitude towards it. From the above discussion, it is clear that proper understanding of e-learning among all teachers is a prerequisite. As they are the future builder of the nation, they need to be technologically advanced to compete in challenging situations. Thus, students and teachers should be well acquainted with e-learning or online teaching and learning. Also, there is a need to develop appropriate strategies that can improve their knowledge and skills related to e-learning. The researcher wants to know the attitude of teachers towards online teaching learning. The investigator confined his research work to the teachers of various schools and colleges.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the effect of gender on the attitude of teachers towards online teaching and learning.
2. To study the effect of locality on the attitude of teachers towards online teaching and learning with respect to locality.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

- H_{0G} : There exists no significant difference in the teachers towards online teaching and learning with respect to gender.
- H_{0L} : There exists no significant difference in the attitude of students towards online teaching and learning with respect to locality.

METHODOLOGY

Design of the study

Descriptive survey method was used to collect the data. Both quantitative and qualitative approach was taken for this research. The questionnaire Survey is designed to collect data from various teachers of schools and colleges of Hooghly district. The present study aims at the attitude of students of West Bengal towards online teaching and learning during the period of COVID 19 pandemic along with their gender and location. The study used a descriptive survey method to determine the attitude towards 'online teaching and learning' and related inferential statistics of parametric statistics.

Population and Sample

The population of this study comprises of male and female teachers in West Bengal Board of Secondary Education schools and the University of Burdwan affiliated colleges in district Hooghly only. Two sub-divisions from Hooghly district were randomly selected. Two blocks from each of the sub-division were randomly selected. Two Schools and one college were randomly selected from each block. Thus, multi-stage sampling was adopted to select the sample for the present study. A sample of 150 teachers from high schools and colleges was randomly selected. 15 teachers were interviewed to check the quality of the sample data. (Online Survey data September 2021)

Delimitation of the Study

Sample was collected from school affiliated to West Bengal Board of Secondary Education in Hooghly district of West Bengal only and College affiliated to the University of Burdwan of West Bengal.

Tool

A questionnaire of attitude towards online teaching and learning developed by the researcher was used for data collection.

The questionnaire is a five point Likert scale. Positive items carries the weights 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 respectively for the categories of strongly disagree, Disagree, Undecided, Agree, Strongly Agree. Negative items are scored as 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively strongly disagree, Disagree, Undecided, Agree, Strongly Agree.

Statistical techniques used

Mean Standard deviation and t -test were used to compare the attitude towards online teaching and learning among teachers with respect Gender and locality.

Data Analysis and Discussion of Results

In this section, attitude towards online teaching and learning among teachers are compared with respect to gender.

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig.(2-tailed)
Male	88	44.33	8.96	-1.528	0.138
Female	62	50.00	6.11		

Table 1: Represents the mean, Standard deviation and t-value attitude towards online teaching and learning among teachers with respect to gender.

Above descriptive presentation describes that the t-value of -1.528 for mean scores for attitude towards online teaching and learning among teachers with respect to gender is not significant. H_{0G} : Null hypothesis accepted. Hence, there is no statistically significant difference in attitude towards online teaching and learning between male and female teachers. In terms of the mean scores female students were found to have a slightly higher mean attitude towards online learning than their male counterparts. It shows that female students have somewhat positive attitude towards online teaching and learning.

In this section, attitude towards online teaching and learning among students are compared with respect to locality.

Location	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig.(2-tailed)
Rural	67	40.62	7.09	-3.216	.003
Urban	83	49.18	7.32		

Table-2: Represents the mean, SD and t-value of attitude towards online teaching and learning between rural and urban teachers.

Above descriptive presentation shows that the t value of -3.216 for mean score for attitude towards online teaching and learning rural and urban teachers is statistically significant. H_{0G} : Null hypothesis rejected. Hence, there is a significant difference in attitude towards online teaching and learning among teachers with locality. In terms of mean score urban students were found to have a higher mean score attitude towards online teaching and learning than their counterparts.

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. Gender has no statistically significant effect on teachers' attitude towards online teaching and learning. However female students have high positive attitude towards online teaching and learning than their male counterparts. The result is coherent with the findings of Kar (2020) and Singh (2021). But the mean score for males and females indicates that male teachers develop a more favorable attitude towards online teaching and learning than female teachers during lockdown which is contrary to this present study.
2. Locality has a statistically significant effect on teachers' attitude towards online teaching and learning. Urban students have favorable attitude towards online teaching and learning than their rural counterparts. Moreover, non-availability of technological resources like computer, tabs and webcam may reason for not so favorable towards online teaching and learning among rural teachers. Teachers in rural areas have always acknowledged the problem of not having a high-speed network. The teacher also admits to facing difficulties in operating the mobile or webcam when using the white board and marker pen without an assistant. The result is somewhat compatible with the findings of Singh (2021); Srivastava & Srivastava (2022) the urban teachers are somewhat technology friendly, but they are not comfortable taking classes online. They were not familiar with the applications used for teaching. Network connection and data speed were also a problem, while in rural areas, most teachers did not have laptops, smartphones, etc.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The findings of the study have direct implications for education especially in this pandemic situation. After a critical analysis of data collected from school and College teachers it was concluded that the attitude towards online teaching during the COVID 19 lockdown is not at all satisfactory. They may not have prior knowledge of online teaching and may be uncomfortable with ICT skills. Most of the teachers also admit to face difficulties in operating the mobile or

webcam when using the white board and marker pen without an assistant. Some of the teachers in rural areas have always acknowledged the problem of not having a highspeed network. All educational institutions should provide usable virtual classrooms. All teachers will provide teaching using the infrastructure of their own educational institution. Central and state governments will jointly provide grants for infrastructure development to provide and maintain usable virtual classrooms to all educational institutions.

As the paradigm shifts from traditional teaching methods to technology enabled learning, it is essential that instructors be well prepared to utilize new technologies to meet the needs of all students (Marzilli et al., 2014). The results of this study revealed that female teachers develop a more favorable attitude towards online teaching than male teachers during the lockdown. This finding is similar to the finding of Alenezi (2012). He found that women's perception of e-learning was more positive than men's. In the context of online teaching during the pandemic situation, most of the female teachers are more active in teaching from home as it does not waste their time traveling to and from educational institutions. Hence women teachers have good attitude towards home teaching materials.

All these online education related issues should be taken very seriously as technology will continue to flow as an integral part of every aspect of human life especially education. Educational institutions can use both online and on campus teaching materials as two tools.

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